

Studies on the Sorption and Desorption of Crystal Violet on and from Bentonite and Kaolinite

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Adsorption isotherms of crystal violet, a triphenylmethane dye, on H-bentonite and H-kaolinite are of the Langmuir-type. No exact correspondence between the cation exchange capacities of the clays and the sorbed amount of dye is noticed. Both the clays take up dyes in excess of their exchange capacities. Adsorption of the whole unionised dye-molecules in the interlamellar spaces and a possible dimerisation of the dye on clay surfaces are suggested as an explanation. The exchangeability of the adsorbed dye with smaller quaternary organic cations is poor. The effect of increasing the alkyl chain-length of the quaternary cations up to four carbon atoms is found to be insignificant. The surface active quaternary cations are far more effective as desorbing agent. A maximum of 80% of kaolinite-bound dye and 30% of bentonite-bound dye are found to be displaced by cetylpyridinium ion. The ability of the cetyltrimethylammonium and cetylpyridinium ion to open up the clay lattices considerably seems to help the interlamellar dyes to diffuse out. The detergent property of such ions is also operative.

The adsorption of organic dyestuffs by clays has been the subject of fairly extensive study^{5,6,7,8,9,10}. Nearly all these studies are aimed at providing an alternative method for determination of the cation exchange capacity and calculation of specific surface areas^{5,6,7,8}. Quite a few of them deal with the mechanism of binding involved^{4,5,6}. However, a detailed study of the desorption of the dye is likely to be of much help in elucidation of such mechanism. Unfortunately, the number of such investigations made so far is not large. De *et al.*⁸ recently reported desorption of clay-bound dye by inorganic and organic cations. In the present study the adsorption of a triphenylmethane dye has been studied. The exchangeability of the clay-bound dye for surface active and non-surface active quaternary organic cations has been followed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Bentonite clay from Akli, Rajasthan (supplied by Geological Survey of India) and a kaolinite clay (supplied by the Calcutta Mineral Supply Corporation) are employed in the study. A clay fraction of minus 1.0μ is isolated by the usual method, dispersed in water and converted to H-form by treatment with H-resin (Amberlite IR-120). The sample of crystal violet (B.D.H., A.R.) is further purified by repeated crystallisation from hot water and vacuum dried.

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All the quaternary compounds employed (except cetylpyridinium bromide) are B.D.H. (A.R.) grade sample. Cetylpyridinium sample is Fluka make.

Adsorption and desorption experiments are carried out in stoppered pyrex bottles of 7.5 c.m. height and 4 cm diameter. Preliminary trial experiments proved that sorption by the walls of the vessel was negligible. A time of exactly 24 hrs. was allowed for equilibration in a thermostat adjusted to 20°.

10 ml portion of kaolinite (0.78%) and bentonite (0.83%) suspensions are taken in the bottles and mixed with gradually increasing quantities of dye beginning with half the c.e.c. amount, and ending with a little over two and half times the c.e.c. Total volumes are made up to 20 ml with water.

After centrifugation, filtration and proper dilution the supernatant is examined at 595 nm in Hilger Uvispeck spectrophotometer for the determination of the equilibrium dye concentration. From the drop in dye concentration the amount sorbed is calculated.

The clay-dye complex is prepared by mixing the dispersed clay with dye solution containing the dye equivalent to twice the exchange capacity, shaking constantly and centrifuging after twenty four hours the supernatant liquid. The complex is freed from adhering dye by repeated washing with deionised water (10 washings). It is then dried for 4 hr at 100° and finally vacuum-dried for 2 days. Tetramethylammonium(TMA⁺), chloride, tetraethylammonium (TEA⁺), tetra-*n*-butylammonium (TBA⁺) bromide, cetyltrimethylammonium (CTA⁺) bromide and cetylpyridinium (CP⁺) bromide are employed as desorbing agents.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results are plotted in Figs. 1 to 3. The Langmuir-type adsorption is observed at the low concentration region, but a clear tendency to multilayer formation at higher dye concentration is noticed from the shape of the isotherms. From the plateaus of the isotherms, 100 g of H-bentonite is found to take up a maximum of 86 me of crystal violet (CV)

Fig. 1

from solution whereas for kaolinite the value is 7 me. No exact correspondence between the c.e.c. and the extent of adsorption is observed. The c.e.c. values determined by the $\text{BaCl}_2/\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ method⁸ are 71 and 3.7 me per 100 g for bentonite and kaolinite respectively. The c.e.c. values cannot, therefore, be calculated from the adsorption data of crystal violet. In fact, the adsorption of the dye is in excess of the c.e.c. which suggests that a significant amount of the sorbed dye is bound to the clay surface by a mechanism other than cation exchange. There is the possibility of adsorption of the unionised dye molecule. Another

Fig. 2

possibility is dimerisation of the dye molecule on the clay surfaces at higher dye concentration. Spectrophotometric measurements¹¹ suggests strongly in favour of dimerisation.

The exchangeability of the clay-bound dye with quaternary cations seems to be poor with the exception of the surface-active ones (Figs. 2, 3). TMA^+ , TEA^+ and TBA^+ released only an insignificant amount of the dye from the clay-dye complexes. However, the release

Fig. 3

of dye by such cations from the kaolinite-dye complexes is somewhat more pronounced than from bentonite-dye complexes. The sorbed dye perhaps finds place in the interlamellar

space of the bentonite and hence less accessible to desorbing ions, whereas the dye attached to the edges of the kaolinite particles becomes more accessible.

The surface-active cations CTA⁺ and CP⁺ both release much higher percentage of the originally bound dye from the clay-dye complex. A maximum of about 32% of the bentonite-bound dye and 80% of the kaolinite-bound dye is released by such cations. The ability of the bentonite particles to swell to a considerable extent^{1,2} might have helped the interlamellar dyes to diffuse out into the aqueous phase. An almost complete removal of the dye from the kaolinite surface is due to the distinct detergent effect of the cetylpyridinium and cetyltrimethylammonium cations. Cetylpyridinium ion is proved to be a better desorbing agent than cetyltrimethyl ammonium ion. This fact can be correlated with the lower critical micelle concentration of the former as shown earlier by De *et al.*⁸ The possibility of dye-detergent interaction¹² was taken care of. It was found that interaction between the cationic dye, CV and the cationic detergents under consideration is negligible at the concentrations at which the experiments had been carried out.

The effect of increasing the chain length of the alkyl radicals on the smaller quaternary cations on their desorbing capacity is not significant up to four carbon atoms. The tetramethylammonium ion hardly releases any dye from the bentonite dye complex, whereas with the kaolinite-dye complex the order of efficiency is TMA⁺ < TEA⁺ < TBA⁺

REFERENCES

1. R. M. Barrer and D. N. Mcleod, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1966, **51**, 129.
2. R. M. Barrer and J. S. S. Reay, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, **53**, 1253.
3. P. Franzen, *Clays Min. Bull.*, 1954, **2**, 223.
4. K. Bergman and P. T. O'Konskii, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, **67**, 2169.
5. F. Paneth, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1922, **101**, 1480, 445.
6. R. N. Plesch and R. M. S. Robertson, *Nature*, 1948, **161**, 1020.
7. W. S. Ramchandran, K. P. Kacker and N. P. Patwardhan, *Amer. Mineralogist*, 1962, **47**, 165.
8. D. K. De, S. K. Chakravarti and S. K. Mukherjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 743.
9. U. Hoffman, *Angew. Chem. Intern. Edn. Engl.*, 1967, **54**, 97.
10. R. K. Chatterjee, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1969, **17**, 317.
11. D. N. Ghosal. (in press).
12. R. Haque and W. Malik, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, **67**, 2082.